

Colombian Network on High Energy Physics

Input on Theoretical HEP

Abstract:

This white paper summarizes the activities of the Colombian community concerning some theoretical aspects of high energy physics that are driving our research. In particular we want to highlight synergistic efforts done in the areas of dark matter, cosmology, flavor and hadron physics. This document summarises the current status and interests of the different groups working on Theoretical High Energy Physics in Colombia, and their perspectives for the future.

Scientific Context:

The Colombian High Energy Physics community has steadily been growing in the last decade, with young scientists taking leading positions at local universities and more students joining this field of research. There are existing collaborations between different groups in the network, with scientists working together from different locations. Topics include flavour physics, Beyond the Standard Model phenomenology, astroparticle physics, cosmology and dark matter. In this context, we organize yearly since 2016 the Colombian meeting of High Energy Physics (COMHEP).

COMHEP (Colombian meeting of High Energy Physics)

The COMHEP is the annual Colombian meeting of high energy physics. We aim to bring together young and senior particle physicists from Colombia and abroad, to discuss recent progress in particle physics, cosmology and related areas. The program of the meeting typically address a broad range of topics, such as: Standard Model and beyond, Neutrino physics , Hadron and flavor physics, Dark matter, Cosmology, Cosmic rays and Future experiments.

COMHEP 2016 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/comhep>)

Nov. 28 - Dec. 2, 2016. ITM.

COMHEP 2017 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/comhep2>)

Dec. 4 - 7, 2017. Universidad Nacional de Colombia.

COMHEP 2018 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/comhep3>)

Dec. 3 - 7, 2018. Universidad Santiago de Cali.

COMHEP 2019 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/comhep4>)

Dec. 2 - 6, 2019. Universidad del Atlántico.

COMHEP 2020

Nov. 30 - Dec. 4, 2020. UPTC.

Community Report on DARK MATTER

There is compelling evidence for the existence of Dark Matter (DM), an unknown, non-baryonic matter component whose abundance in the Universe exceeds the amount of ordinary matter roughly by a factor of five. Still, the non-gravitational nature of DM remains a mystery. The fact that the observed abundances of dark and visible matter are in the same ballpark may be considered as indicative that both forms of matter have a common origin and they were once in thermal equilibrium with each other. Despite the fact that DM has been searched for decades, the studies have yielded no overwhelming evidence for what DM actually is.

Here we want to highlight the main physics open questions that have been driving the research of our community:

1. Dark Matter production in the early universe

- WIMP mechanism

In the previous decades, this class of scenarios has received by far the biggest attention, both theoretically and experimentally. WIMPs (Weakly Interacting Massive Particles) typically carry electroweak scale mass and couple to the SM with a strength that is reminiscent to that of the weak interactions.

- FIMP mechanism

The observed DM abundance may have been generated also out of equilibrium by the so-called freeze-in mechanism. In this scenario, the DM particle couples to the visible SM sector very weakly, so that it never entered chemical equilibrium. Instead, the DM particles were produced by decay or annihilation processes from the visible sector. Due to the small coupling strength, the DM particles produced via the freeze-in mechanism have been called Feebly Interacting Massive Particles (FIMPs).

- Axions and axion-like particles

Axions and axion-like particles are also very popular DM candidates that could be related to the solution of the strong CP-problem in QCD. A very light axion is stable and constitutes a natural DM candidate.

- Non-standard cosmologies

It is typically assumed that after inflation the evolution of the universe is driven by the SM radiation energy density and that the SM entropy is conserved. However, that should not be the case. Alternatively, one can also consider non-standard cosmological histories, for example scenarios where the universe was effectively matter-dominated at an early stage, due to a slow reheating period after inflation or to a massive metastable particle. There are no indispensable reasons to assume that the Universe was radiation-dominated prior to Big Bang Nucleosynthesis. These scenarios drastically modify the prediction of the DM relic abundance.

2. Dark Matter production at Colliders

- DM searches with CMS

CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) is a particle detector at the LHC. It has a broad physics program to search for physics beyond the Standard Model, including DM. The effort of the experimental groups of the community involved, concentrate on

DM searches using supersymmetric models in compressed mass spectra scenarios with tau leptons. The searches are carried out using two different techniques, vector boson fusion and jets from initial state radiation. In addition, the team has conducted searches for DM considering the production of heavy neutrinos with right-handed helicity in final states with tau leptons and jets. It is important to mention that several papers have been published on these topics with strong involvement and leadership from Colombian researchers.

- DM searches with DUNE

The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) is an ambitious project currently under construction. The experiment will have a high-intensity proton beam, with either 60 or 120 GeV energies. Due to this high energy, it is possible to create a new dark sector mediator or new DM particles from meson decays. Such dark sector particles (mediators and DM) could then be detected at the Near Detector from its interactions with the liquid Argon. Currently, Colombian institutions are developing models where DM particles interact via a dark photon. In this way, the dark photon could kinetically mix with the SM photon such as to generate interactions with the SM quarks or leptons that could be detected by the near detector's sensors. The goal is to impose constraints on the models that arise from different experiments (collider production, astrophysical experiments, etc) and then explore DUNE's sensitivity to the available parameter space.

3. Dark Matter Direct and Indirect Detection

Even if the Colombian community is not directly involved in any experimental collaboration aiming to directly or indirectly detect the DM particles, we make use of the measurements and bounds.

As a community, we understand that the absence of a Colombian participation on the worldwide effort of detecting DM particles via direct and indirect detection experiments is a big issue that has to be solved in the near future.

4. *N*-body simulations

According to astrophysics and cosmology, DM is a major constituent of the Universe that plays a fundamental role in the formation of structures and galaxies. This makes these astrophysical phenomena, one of the best scenarios to study the nature of DM. In that sense, *N*-body simulations of the formation of structures and *N*-body simulations of dynamics of galaxies become an important framework to study the properties and detectability of DM.

Current *N*-body simulations of structure formation allow to study the spatial properties of DM, clustering and substructure abundance. All these subjects turn into important keys in the understanding of the properties of DM. In these simulations standard (LCDM) and non-standard (self-interacting, decaying DM, etc.) scenarios can be explored with the aim to contrast the predictions of many different physical scenarios against the observations.

Another subject where *N*-body simulations can shed light on the properties of DM is the study of dynamics of galaxies, and particularly merging galaxies. During the merger of galaxies, structures like streams, plumes and rings of material emerge as a result of the gravitational interaction. The structure and dynamics of such structures depends closely on the properties of the DM and turns in a different scenario to study its properties. A problem

that can be tackled by making use of N -body simulations and that can be directly connected to what can be measured from observations.

5. Astrophysical and Cosmological probes of Dark Matter

DM self-interactions could give a handle in solving long-standing problems in DM halos at small scales. Observations of the small scale structure and cluster mergers may provide important insight into the non-gravitational interactions inside the dark sector.

Additionally, isocurvature fluctuation modes are a generic feature of models where feebly coupled scalar fields exist in the dark sector. They arise from density fluctuations of dark sector scalar fields, in the case that the energy density stored in a scalar field at the end of inflation is deposited into DM. These modes are severely constrained by the CMB power spectrum.

Finally, the recent experimental success in observing gravitational waves has opened up a new avenue for observational cosmology, which will be further enhanced by, for example, the upcoming LISA mission. Gravitational waves produced in dark sector phase transitions could be observed with the LISA experiment, regardless of the weakness of non-gravitational interactions between the dark and visible sectors.

6. Dark Matter connections to other open problem beyond the Standard Model

- Electroweak phase transitions

The presence of DM particles may induce significant changes on the scalar potential of the Standard Model in such a way the electroweak symmetry breaking turns out to be a strong first order phase transition. This feature would make viable electroweak baryogenesis as the solution to the matter-antimatter asymmetry.

- Strong CP problem

The Peccei-Quinn solution to this problem brings along with the axion, which constitutes a viable DM candidate.

- Neutrino masses

The heavy new particles usually used to explain the smallness of neutrino masses can be easily accommodated in the dark sector where the lightest particle can be identified as the dark matter particle.

- Inflation

The field responsible for the early expansion period of the Universe (the inflaton) may serve as a DM candidate.

MOCa (Materia Oscura en Colombia).

The *Colombian Workshop on Dark Matter* (MOCa) is an initiative that arises as a response to the need to strengthen the Colombian community working on several aspects related to the DM. It is important to mention that in the country we are reaching a critical mass, and we are already working on different subjects like particle physics, cosmology and astrophysics, but also in the theoretical, experimental and phenomenological fronts. In that sense DM can be used as an opportunity to make contact between our different expertises, even if for all of us DM is not the main research area.

The workshop has already taken place three times:

MOCa 2017 (<https://forero.github.io/MOCA/>)

From June 17th to June 29th, 19 participants and 12 talks.

MOCa 2018 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/moca2018>)

From July 30th to August 1st, 73 participants and 18 talks.

MOCa 2019 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/moca2019>)

From September 30th to October 2nd, 56 participants and 17 talks. This edition counted with two international invited speakers: Prof. Chee Sheng Fong (UFABC, Brazil) and Prof. James Unwin (Berkeley, USA).

The workshop so far has been held by Universidad de los Andes, and has received financial support by Universidad de los Andes, Universidad Antonio Nariño, ICTP and COLCIENCIAS. These funds are essential especially for supporting students with travel and local expenses.

This meeting will continue in the forthcoming years and will be enlarged with a day devoted to introductory lectures for early stage researchers interested in the field. The MOCa 2020 is planned to occur in the first semester of 2020.

Organizers: Carlos Ávila (Universidad de los Andes), Juan Pablo Beltrán (Universidad Antonio Nariño), Nicolás Bernal (Universidad Antonio Nariño), Andrés Flórez (Universidad de los Andes), Jaime Forero (Universidad de los Andes) and César Valenzuela (Universidad del Valle).

Community Report on COSMOLOGY

Theoretical and observational cosmology is living an exciting age due to the vast number of observational data coming from past, present, and planned missions devoted to measure specific details about the distribution of primordial cosmological (temperature) perturbations in the cosmic microwave background (CMB) and in the present distribution of large scale structures (LSS) in the Universe. This data is making possible for the first time in history to test, compare, constraint and eventually rule out several models proposed as candidates to explain the mechanisms driving the beginning and the evolution at large scales of the Universe.

Here we want to highlight the main physics open questions that have been driving the research of our community:

1. Inflation

Inflation is the current paradigm in cosmology which describes the main features of the early Universe and solves the pressing problems related to fine tuning and causality of the initial conditions of the Big Bang model. The simplest and most successful version of this mechanism requires a single scalar field to drive an exponentially accelerated expansion able to smooth the initial conditions of the Universe and, because of its quantum fluctuations, to generate irregularities in the energy density after horizon exit. Afterwards, via gravitational clustering, it generates the large-scale structure that is seen today. The inflationary mechanism is simple and is able to explain most of the features of the CMB; however, when studying the different implementations of the inflationary idea, we recognize that there is generally a lack of connection of this physics with the low energy particle physics accessible to current experiments. This lack of connection might be due to the vastly different energy scale between inflation and particle physics processes. Thus, if we expect to understand inflation and particle physics in a unified framework, work is needed to connect the physics behind the inflationary mechanism with the particle physics even for models beyond the SM of particle physics.

2. Reheating

At the end of inflation, the universe has grown by a factor of around 60 e -folds and is basically empty. During reheating, the energy density of the inflaton is converted into SM radiation. Several constraints apply in order the observed cosmology takes place. In particular it is desirable that not great amounts of dark radiation is generated during reheating and instead the energy stored in the inflaton is effectively populating via the observable sector.

3. Modified gravity theories

In modified gravity theories it is desirable to reduce the number of free parameters, or better, to have a model-independent way to test large families of theories. The interest of some local groups is to study Horndeski-like theories. In this context, there is a model-independent observable called the anisotropic stress η (or also called gravitational slip) . By combining galaxy clustering and weak lensing probes (the core tools of an Euclid-like survey) a forecast analysis can be carried out to constrain the precision within which the anisotropic stress could be measured. Additional applications of modified gravity

models of current interest for the local groups are astrophysical solutions like black holes and compact object, inflationary solutions, among others.

4. Non-Gaussianity

The interest in these subjects is justified by the fact that non-Gaussianity (NG) and statistical anisotropy signatures in the probability distribution of the CMB temperature anisotropies are sensitive to the specific details of the mechanisms ruling the dynamics of the early Universe; thus, their precise evaluation could provide relevant criteria to discriminate among the many models proposed to explain the origin of the LSS distribution that we observe today. Moreover, the detection of a significant signal of NG and statistical anisotropy would rule out the simplest models of inflation based on a single “slowly rolling” scalar field driving the inflationary mechanism. A possible way to generate significant levels of statistical anisotropy and NG is by introducing vector fields, antisymmetric tensor fields: p -forms, or general gauge fields during the inflationary epoch as a source of the primordial curvature perturbation.

5. Primordial and astrophysical Gravitational Waves

The recent observations of Gravitational waves by LIGO and Virgo paved the way to observe the Universe with new methods not based on electromagnetic radiation. The existence of a PGW background is one of the most crucial predictions of the inflationary scenario of the early Universe. Future gravitational wave observatories like the Einstein Telescope, LISA or BBO, and pulsar timing arrays could start probing the relevant parameter space favoured by a number of inflationary models.

Primordial gravitational waves can be considered as a smoking gun of inflation. Several models of inflation predict specific patterns and amplitudes for the gravitational waves produced during the inflationary epoch. Currently, some local groups have interest in inflationary models in the presence of additional degrees of freedom aside from the inflaton scalar field. Those models include typically couplings with gauge fields and non minimal couplings with gravity. The particular features of the gravitational waves depend on the particular kind of couplings and can be constrained with CMB data.

6. Large Scale Structures Formation

Large-Scale Structure of the Universe refers to the distribution of matter in the largest observable scales that is bound together by the gravitational force. Structure formation is the process whereby a tiny spatial perturbation in the matter distribution becomes more inhomogeneous with the passage of time, due to the gravitational instability of matter, until galaxies, clusters of galaxies and superclusters become formed. The widely accepted mechanism to seed the Universe with an initially tiny matter inhomogeneities is Cosmological Inflation. Current and future experiments will allow us to build a three-dimensional map of the structures that make up our Universe. With the data from these missions, we expect to have a precise temporal evolution of the growth of the structures at cosmological scales, which will allow, for example, to an accurate description of the dark energy.

7. Dark Energy

In the late 90s, two independent groups discovered that the Universe is actually engaging

into a period of accelerated expansion. Since then, a number of theoretical avenues have been investigated to explain it. Although the simplest explanation is in favour of a cosmological constant, its required value is very small when compared with theoretical expectations, that other alternatives have been put forward to explain the observed cosmic acceleration without having to resort to unnaturally small parameters. The two most popular alternatives to a cosmological constant are the dark energy, a hypothesized new form of matter making up about 68% of the Universe's energy, and the modification of the theory of gravity allowed due to the poor experimental constraints of the general relativity theory on large scales. Currently, these alternatives remain plausible explanations of the cosmic acceleration and, however, they entail radically different implications for the physical theories describing nature. Owing to this, the discovery of the agent causing the late-time cosmic acceleration (either cosmological constant, dark energy or modified gravity) has become one of the most pressing questions in theoretical cosmology.

8. UV completions

From the perspective of a consistent quantum description one has to rely on models resulting for example from string compactifications. These models, despite being in principle consistent, come with many extra ingredients, for example several scalar fields and definite couplings with the matter sector. This not only allows to rule out plenty of models but also the construction of models not proposed yet. Although the problem has many points to tackle in general these are encoded in what is called modular cosmology, where the moduli fields can play the role of the inflaton, and in general might produce unwanted non-gaussianities, but also can help to explain a tiny value for the cosmological constant and, since all these scenarios are in a supergravity playground, to break supersymmetry at some stage.

CoCo (Cosmología en Colombia).

The *Colombian Workshop on Cosmology* (CoCo) is an initiative that arises as a response to the need to strengthen the Colombian community working on several cosmological aspects. It is important to mention that in the country we are reaching a critical mass, and we are already working on different subjects like inflation, black holes, dark energy, modified gravity, gravitational waves, large scale structures, N -body simulations and the connection with particle physics. In that sense, cosmology can be used as an opportunity to make contact between our different expertises.

The workshop has already taken place once:

CoCo 2019 (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/coco2019>)

From May 30th to May 31st, 67 participants and 33 talks. This first edition counted with an international invited speaker: Prof. Sergio Palomares-Ruiz (IFIC, Spain).

The workshop was held and funded by Universidad Antonio Nariño. This meeting will continue in the forthcoming years, the CoCo 2020 is planned to occur in the first semester of 2020 at Universidad de los Andes.

Organizers: Juan Pablo Beltrán (Universidad Antonio Nariño), Nicolás Bernal (Universidad Antonio Nariño).

Community Report on HADRON and FLAVOR PHYSICS

The standard model represents the best theory to describe electric and magnetic forces in a unified picture with the weak and the strong forces. However, there are many questions that so far do not have a definitive answer. For example, in the quark sector, there are 10 unknown parameters, 6 masses, 3 mixing angles, and one phase; an equal number of parameters (or even larger for Majorana neutrinos) is needed in the lepton sector. The exact mechanism that originated these scales is unknown; however, over the last decades, several models that address these questions have been proposed. In general, the mechanism that explains these mass scales is part of the so-called flavor problem.

1. Beyond the standard model and flavor physics

- Electroweak Extensions of the Standard Model

Some of these questions can be answered by introducing an additional electroweak sector. In particular, flavored symmetries result quite useful to address the replication problem, the mass hierarchies, and even charge quantization. The idea heavily relies on the cancellation of the chiral anomalies, which represent quantum constraints on the gauge charges of chiral models. It is important to highlight that many research groups in Colombia have worked on 331 models and on models with a non-universal Z' which usually are suitable to address flavor problems.

- Discrete and global symmetries

Discrete and global symmetries result quite useful to explain the standard model mass scales and CP violating phases. In many cases, It is possible to obtain these symmetries as residual symmetries of gauge group interactions mediated by heavy gauge bosons. In this way, the low energy accidental symmetries could shed light on the underlying physics principles and symmetries at very high energies. The same is true in the phenomenological analysis of the texture-zeros in the quark and lepton mass matrices, which can be considered in many cases as alternatives to impose discrete symmetries.

2. Flavor and hadron physics

- Flavored Bound States

Since the fundamental degrees of freedom of the strong interaction, quarks and gluons, cannot propagate freely through the vacuum, the only states with well-defined properties at low-energies are singlet-color states. The properties of these states are determined by the content of quarks and by the representation of the flavor group to which they belong. Owing to the fact that many of these states are not flavor singlets, all the possible flavor combinations generate a zoo of particles whose spectrum can be explained as bound states of the lighter quarks. Many of these states have a net weak charge. That is important for hydrogen-like atoms since that, in that case, it is possible to make precise theoretical predictions. The strongest constraints on the Z - Z' mixing angle come from the precise measurements of the cesium weak charge.

- Flavor Changing Neutral Currents FCNC

One of the consequences of the family dependent charges are the flavor changing neutral currents FCNC at the tree level, the strongest constraints on these phenomena come from the K_0 - K_0 mixing, which imposes tough restrictions on the new-physics couplings to the left-handed quark doublets of the first and second generation. In the SM, the GIM mechanism avoids FCNC at the tree level; however, it is possible to have FCNC at one-loop order. The precise measurements of these processes represent strong constraints on the electroweak extensions of the SM.

- Lepton universality violation in the B meson decays

The B meson decays have constituted a good scenario for studying, on both theoretical and experimental levels, the Standard Model (SM) as well as for exploring new physics (NP) effects at low-energy scales. Particularly, semileptonic and leptonic B meson decays offer an excellent place to test lepton universality (LU), so far one of the cornerstones of the SM. Any mismatch between the theoretical and experimental predictions may be an indication of LU violation, and therefore a hint of NP beyond the SM.

- Measurements on spectroscopy and Heavy Flavor with CMS

CMS has a broad physics program, including Measurements on spectroscopy and Heavy Flavor, and search for physics beyond the Standard Model. The experimental groups of the community are involved in Leptonic B meson decays, which offers excellent opportunities to perform precision tests of the SM of particle physics because of minimal hadronic uncertainties in the theoretical predictions.

On the other hand, although quantum chromodynamics (QCD) is well established as the theory of the strong interaction, a complete understanding of the (nonperturbative) processes that lead to the binding of quarks and gluons into hadrons is still lacking. The Bc family consists of charged mesons composed of a beauty quark and a charm antiquark (or vice versa), and the bottomonium family, composed of beauty quark-antiquark bound states, play a special role in understanding how the strong force binds quarks into hadrons. It is important to say that our groups are strongly involved in this research field and several of the results released by the CMS collaboration on these issues were led by our researchers.

List of the interested scientists in the community:

- Mario A. Acero Ortega (Universidad del Atlántico)
- Enrique Arrieta Díaz (Universidad del Magdalena)
- Carlos Ávila (Universidad de los Andes)
- Juan Pablo Beltrán (Universidad Antonio Nariño)
- Nicolás Bernal (Universidad Antonio Nariño)
- Amalia Betancur (Universidad EIA)
- Andres Castillo (Universidad Sergio Arboleda)
- Andrés Flórez (Universidad de los Andes)
- Diego Gallego (UPTC)
- Yithsbey Giraldo (Universidad de Nariño)
- Luz Stella Gomez (Universidad Sergio Arboleda)
- Jhovanny Andrés Mejía Guisado (Universidad de Antioquia)
- Deywis Moreno (Universidad Antonio Nariño)
- Alexander Moreno Briceño (Universidad Antonio Nariño)
- Gabriela Navarro (Universidad Antonio Nariño)
- Diego Restrepo (Universidad de Antioquia)
- Eduardo Rojas (Universidad de Nariño)
- José David Ruiz Álvarez (Universidad de Antioquia)
- César Valenzuela (Universidad del Valle)
- Nelson Vanegas (Universidad de Antioquia)
- David Vanegas Forero (Universidad de Medellín)
- Carlos Yaguna (UPTC)
- Óscar Zapata (Universidad de Antioquia)